

Theory of Objective Material Deprivation: A Normative Framework for the Analysis of Political Injustice and Civic Mobilization

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1. Introduction

A. Fundamental normative level: judgment on legitimacy

An interpretation is normative when it is not limited to describing causal relationships, but rather: a) evaluates the moral legitimacy of state actions, institutions, and responses, and b) introduces normative criteria of justice and injustice.

In this book, I argue that civic rebellions originating in objective material deprivation are morally understandable and normatively justifiable, while the political order that produces and reproduces such deprivation loses legitimacy. This statement does not constitute an empirical claim, but rather a normative judgment concerning state responsibility, the right to resist and the limits of civil obedience.

In the tradition of political philosophy, Locke bases rebellion as a right of resistance; Rousseau links it to popular legitimacy; Rawls, to the conditions of basic justice. The central difference of the thesis

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presented here lies in the fact that it postulates a material, and not merely procedural, foundation of civic rebellions.

B. Normative delimitation criteria

By addressing the notion of "civic rebellion" and distinguishing it from criminal behaviour, this book introduces normative criteria that allow the conceptual delimitation of both phenomena. These criteria include:

1. The origin in an objective material deprivation, thus differentiating itself from actions motivated by opportunism.
2. The reactive nature in the face of unjust policies, understood as expressions of structural injustice.
3. The initial absence of an instrumentalized leadership that directs collective action from its initial phase.
4. The collapse of the institutional channels aimed at correcting these situations.

These criteria configure a normative typology, and not merely a descriptive one, and allow us to answer the following central question:

When does a violent collective action cease to be a simple disorder and become a civic rebellion with normative relevance?

C. Imputation of duties to the State

The Theory of Objective Material Deprivation does not limit itself to explaining the genesis of social protest but also imputes specific obligations to the State. These include:

(i) the duty to guarantee minimum material conditions for the population; (ii) the duty to avoid policies that violate basic subsistence thresholds; (iii) the duty to refrain from resorting to the use of military force as a mechanism of internal government.

In this sense, the assertion that state repression aggravates the illegitimacy of the political order constitutes, above all, a normative judgment about the obligations of the state vis-à-vis the citizenry.

2. A theoretical model that anticipates social unrest in response to rising poverty:

My analysis is based on the belief that extreme poverty shapes motivations for collective action differently than relative deprivation, emphasizing the importance of objective material conditions over subjective perceptions.

In countries like Chile, where one percent owns almost a third of all wealth, extreme poverty coexists with the public display of affluence and luxury by the upper and middle classes. In this space, the disadvantaged hardly have the opportunity to "perceive" a possibility of overcoming their destitution within the framework of the socio-economic and cultural system at their disposal. They can dream, but they can also act.

Especially when the few social achievements they have achieved with certain progressive legislations are taken away from them by political programs of ultraliberal/authoritarian orientation, discriminatory and anti-popular that seize state power.

The causal dynamic of mobilization does not revolve in the subjective perception that others can enjoy better rights and better goods. Instead, political mobilization is driven by the lived reality of severe material deprivation.

Definition and Axioms of Objective Material Deprivation

Objective Material Deprivation is understood as a structural condition in which certain social groups lack the minimum material means necessary to reproduce their daily lives.

This situation occurs regardless of the subjective expectations of the individuals themselves or of any social comparison with other groups. That is, deprivation does not depend on relative perceptions or feelings, but on the real and tangible absence of resources indispensable for daily subsistence.

Explaining the general axiom that derives from this definition: in societies characterized by high structural inequality, a significant increase in objective material poverty represents a sufficient condition for spontaneous civic rebellions to arise as a reaction to regressive state policies. Formulating the axiom:

In societies with high structural inequality, a significant increase in objective material poverty is a sufficient condition for the emergence of spontaneous civic rebellions against regressive state policies.

That is, when material conditions worsen significantly and the State implements measures that further aggravate the situation of the most vulnerable, the collective response tends to be immediate and arises from the experience of deprivation itself.

Applying this principle to the Chilean case, it can be seen that, historically, the intensification of objective material poverty, together with the suppression or increase in the price of essential goods that were previously guaranteed, has recurrently generated spontaneous social outbursts.

These episodes are not usually directed by political parties or formal leaderships but are born from the existential experience of exclusion and conditions of critical subsistence. This social response also acquires a moral legitimacy that is based on material suffering and on the refusal to accept living conditions considered unacceptable.

Objective material deprivation refers to the tangible and measurable lack of essential resources or needs experienced by individuals or groups. This includes, but is not limited to, factors such as income inequality, insufficient access to basic services such as health, education and housing, persistent food insecurity and poor living conditions.

In contrast to relative deprivation, which depends on personal perceptions or social comparisons, objective material deprivation is based on real, quantifiable hardships that individuals endure, regardless of their expectations or how they compare to others. Although the concept of material deprivation has been widely debated, I focus explicitly on objective and measurable deprivation, separate from relative perceptions

While theories of relative deprivation suggest that distress arises from feelings of deserving more or having less than others, the objective theory of material deprivation emphasizes the actual presence (and preeminence) of fundamental needs.

Here, the problem is not what people "think" they are missing, but what they really lack, such as safe housing, sufficient income, or access to education. For those living in extreme poverty, the driving force behind protest or political action is the lived experience of deprivation itself, not a comparison to others.

Refuting Gurr's theory of relative deprivation

As described above, Ted Robert Gurr's (1970) Theory of Relative Deprivation focuses on the idea that political violence, protest, and revolution are driven by the perceived gap between what individuals or groups believe they deserve and what they actually possess or can get.

In this framework, the perception of deprivation – formed through expectations, social comparisons or relative status – acts as a catalyst for unease. Importantly, this theory explains how groups that may be objectively better off than others can continue to feel marginalized and mobilize against perceived injustice. The key idea here is that relative deprivation is not just the experience of those living in absolute poverty; Rather, inequality and unmet expectations can provoke collective action across socioeconomic strata.

Instead, the material deprivation approach focuses on the direct experience of poverty and its role in political mobilization. This perspective holds that, for those living in extreme poverty, the problem goes beyond feelings of entitlement or expectations: it is rooted in the tangible difficulties they face on a daily basis.

For these people, "misery" is not a subjective feeling but a lived reality, and it becomes a clear trigger for action when their conditions are perceived as unjust. Political mobilization, in this framework, occurs mainly when there are real increases in material deprivation, especially among the most economically vulnerable. Unlike Gurr's theory, this approach emphasizes objective poverty and true deprivation suffered, such as lack of access to basic necessities, as the direct impetus for collective action.

The fundamental difference between these frameworks lies in their approach: Gurr's model focuses on relative deprivation, highlighting how inequality or unmet expectations can incite unease, even among those who do not experience absolute poverty.

By contrast, the material deprivation approach emphasizes the importance of real and worsening material conditions as the driving force behind political mobilization. From this perspective, it is the objective reality of poverty, rather than relative frustration or

comparison, that drives groups to protest or rebel in response to a perceived systemic injustice.

In other words:

The *Theory of Relative Deprivation* holds that social protests emerge when individuals perceive a discrepancy between their expectations and what they believe they can legitimately attain. That is, collective action originates in the subjective perception that a better situation than the present one deserves. Social comparison and unfulfilled expectations are, in this framework, the fundamental drivers of discontent and mobilization.

On the contrary, the *Theory of Objective Material Deprivation* states that rebellion does not arise from perceptions or comparisons with other groups, but as a direct response to a real, tangible and inescapable condition of material damage. In this approach, collective action is not the result of relative feelings of injustice, but of the effective impossibility of continuing to subsist under the existing social order. It is the immediate experience of misery and exclusion, and not the feeling of deserving of something more, that drives the most disadvantaged social groups to rebel:

The poor do not rebel because they believe they deserve more; they rebel because they can no longer live with less.

In short, from the perspective of objective material deprivation, it is understood that the poor do not rebel because they believe they deserve more, but because they have reached a point where they can no longer live with less. Social mobilization is thus interpreted as an inevitable reaction to the extreme degradation of material living conditions, without the need for subjective or comparative mediation.

Justice from the Capabilities Approach and the Theory of Objective Material Deprivation

The capabilities approach proposed by Amartya Sen proposes a vision of justice that transcends formal procedures and focuses on people's real possibilities. According to this approach, justice is not only about having abstract rights or norms, but about ensuring that individuals have the *effective capacity to lead lives that they consider valuable* (Sen, 1999; 2009). In this sense, what is important is not only the existence of rules, but the concretization of those rules into tangible opportunities for human development. That is, in the real possibility of converting rights into basic functionings, such as food, travel, work, and access to health and education.

The Theory of Objective Material Deprivation is inscribed in this perspective, but it specifies it from a specific normative angle: it identifies political injustice fundamentally where those basic capacities are *materially impossible*. From this point of view, the objective deprivation of essential needs constitutes a primary form of injustice, insofar as it blocks the effective exercise of rights and the realization of basic functionings.

Both perspectives coincide in underlining the centrality of material conditions for social justice. However, while the capabilities approach operates as a general normative criterion for the evaluation of justice, the TPMO focuses on the identification of *objective material thresholds*, the transgression of which not only reveals the existence of an unjust situation but also establishes a sufficient condition for the erosion of political legitimacy and for the emergence of civic mobilization.

The direct link between material deprivation and political mobilization

Objective material deprivation is presented as a sufficient condition for the political mobilization of economically vulnerable groups. When these groups face worsening material circumstances—such as growing poverty or the erosion of social welfare—this directly fuels their motivation to challenge policies they perceive as unfair. For example, workers' protests can be attributed to increased material hardship, such as the rising cost of living, rising unemployment, and insufficient access to public services, rather than mere perceptions of inequality.

Normative corollary

According to the Theory of Objective Material Deprivation, any policy of extreme austerity applied to populations that are already impoverished has serious consequences not only in the social sphere, but also in the political sphere. These measures, far from being limited to being socially regressive, generate structural conditions that are sufficient to activate civic rebellion among the most disadvantaged sectors.

The fundamental reason is that, under this approach, the collective response does not arise from subjective comparisons or unfulfilled expectations, but from the immediate and tangible experience of poverty.

Thus, policies that further aggravate the material situation of those who already live in unacceptable conditions trigger an inevitable reaction: the mobilization of the social groups affected.

This shows that such policies not only deepen exclusion and suffering, but also put political stability at risk, by promoting scenarios of protest and rebellion motivated by the impossibility of continuing to accept an extreme degradation of living conditions.

An empirically anchored normative theory with predictive capacity

What is being proposed should not be understood as a simple variant of pre-existing theories on social mobilization, but as the formulation of a normative theory endowed with predictive capacity, deeply anchored in the concrete historical experience of Chile over more than a century.

This proposal is distinguished by its focus on objective material conditions as the basis of collective action, rather than on subjective perceptions of injustice alone. Consequently, the theory holds that rebellions and social mobilization emerge not by mere comparison with what is considered deserved, but as an inevitable response to the extreme and tangible degradation of living conditions.

The normative nature of the theory lies in the fact that it allows us to identify the policies and structural conditions that, inevitably, generate scenarios of protest and political destabilization. At the same time, its predictive capacity is based on the empirical observation of Chilean history, showing how, on a recurring basis, the application of extreme austerity policies to already impoverished populations have led to episodes of civic rebellion and social transformation.

Thus, the proposed theory offers a robust framework to understand and anticipate the social and political risks associated with the deepening of material deprivation, providing tools both for academic analysis and for the formulation of public policies aimed at stability and social justice.

Social and political consequences

a) Political mobilization: People in objectively disadvantaged conditions, especially among the working class, often lack adequate means to address their grievances through conventional channels such

as voting or negotiation. This limitation increases the likelihood of direct actions such as protests, strikes, and revolutions.

It was this type of situation that triggered the *2019 Social Outbreak* in Chile. People impoverished under progressive and precarious material conditions did not find political avenues for their demands. A commonly mentioned critique in the literature that refers to the events of 2019 mentions the functional collapse of the system of political intermediation – including traditional leftist parties – to meet the demands of a vast cohort of the Chilean people, pressured by their objective material conditions of existence. In the end, ontogenetic survival mechanisms constantly prevail and make themselves heard in the socio-political space.

b) Resistance and Revolution: When materially disadvantaged groups perceive that their conditions are being ignored or aggravated by government policies, they may resort to more extreme forms of political violence or organized rebellion, considering such actions as necessary means to demand change.

Structural factors and motivations for action

a) Institutional failures: The Theory of Objective Material Deprivation highlights the role of state structures that do not satisfy basic needs and perpetuate systemic inequality. Policies that favour the elite or overlook the well-being of vulnerable populations act as catalysts for mobilisation, and

b) Economic inequality: Rather than focusing on perceived inequality, the theory highlights real disparities in economic access, opportunity, and wealth distribution.

Unlike theories that are based on the gap between expectation and reality, the Theory of Objective Material Deprivation holds that the

actual conditions of poverty and deprivation are sufficient motivators for action. There is no need for complex psychological processes or subjective interpretations: individuals engage in collective actions because they are experiencing real difficulties that threaten their survival or basic dignity.

Summary and conclusion

(i) Real material deprivation—such as poverty and lack of basic services—is identified as the main driving force for political mobilization among economically vulnerable groups.

(ii) Objective difficulty is distinguished from subjective perceptions and can be measured by specific indicators such as income, housing conditions and access to health care.

iii) Increased material deprivation within individuals or communities can provoke collective action or protest against unjust policies, without requiring a sense of injustice or relative comparison.

(iv) Political mobilization arises as a natural response to worsening material conditions, and affected groups may resort to protest or even violence as a result of these difficulties.

v) Material deprivation as an objective: It emphasizes that deprivation is a real condition that individuals face, not simply a psychological experience.

vi) Political mobilization as a response: The theory affirms that this deprivation is both the trigger and a sufficient condition for political action.

vii) Distinction with respect to relative deprivation: It emphasizes that the theory is concerned with objective conditions, not with subjective comparisons with others.

Historically, a marked increase in poverty has consistently increased the likelihood of actively mobilized protests and social resistance. In the context of Chile, where economic disparities are expected to become even more pronounced quantitatively, in tandem with the austerity measures that are expected to intensify, the difficulties among the poor may increase qualitatively.

A general axiom would be that:

As poverty intensifies, the likelihood of mobilization among working-class, student, and unemployed populations in response to perceived injustice increases.

However, in the case of Chile (and comparable societies), considered historically, the axiom can be stated more clearly:

An increase in poverty is a sufficient condition for the active social mobilization of economically vulnerable groups in the face of policies considered unjust.

This is different from *the theory of relative deprivation* (Gurr, 1970), which explains political violence, protest, and revolution as deriving from the perceived gap between what people believe they deserve and what they actually have, or can get, rather than absolute poverty. As in Gurr's meaning of relative deprivation:

"Actors' perception of the discrepancy between their value expectations and their value capabilities."

My proposition is different from that of Gurr's theory. What I intend to conceptualize (as essential elements behind the causes and motivations of the protests I describe) has to do with *the* real economic deprivation of the impoverished sectors, rather than with the *idea* that – compared to other social classes – they, the poor, *only think* that they should be entitled to more benefits from their society. In my opinion,

it is not only a question of a "subjective perception", but of an existing "objective" misery, and which they must *endure* instead of "perceiving".

In other words, I separate *relative/subjective deprivation* from *objective material deprivation*.

The Hegelian/Marxist theory of *Alienation* explains this problem from another point of view, which would actually be the point of view or conclusion of the alienated worker himself: everyday life can lead him to admire the lifestyle of the bourgeoisie or of any class that has sufficient purchasing power, sufficient time, etc. sufficient rest, etc.

But the propaganda on the part of the ideological/cultural superstructure that he receives leads him to the conclusion that he can only "perceive" a social inequality but that at the same time the "social order" does not allow him to get out of his unfortunate condition (unless he himself can transform himself into an accumulator of capital).

3. Fundamental Bases and Propositions in the Theory of Objective Material Deprivation (TPMO)

P1 – Basic material condition and definition of deprivation

Objective material deprivation is manifested when individuals or groups lack the essential and quantifiable resources that are essential to ensure a dignified life. These resources include, but are not limited to, sufficient income, access to adequate housing, food, health services, and basic education. This condition does not depend on subjective interpretations, since it can be objectively determined and is directly linked to the ability to reproduce life under acceptable conditions.

P2 – Independence from social perception and comparison

Objective material deprivation exists regardless of how it is perceived or evaluated by the affected individuals. It is not related to personal expectations, social comparisons, or normative judgments. Thus, the experience of deprivation does not require those affected to compare their situation with that of other groups or to experience a sense of relative injustice; it is enough to have a direct experience of material poverty for this phenomenon to occur.

P3 – Material tolerance threshold and collective mobilization

Every society establishes a minimum material threshold, below which the continuity of daily life becomes structurally unfeasible for a significant part of the population. The persistent crossing of this threshold constitutes a sufficient condition for collective political mobilization, even in the absence of class consciousness, revolutionary ideology, or organized leadership. Thus, political action can emerge as a response to extreme deprivation, without the need for prior ideological processes.

P4 – Causal sufficiency

The persistent crossing of the minimum material threshold set by society is not simply an indicator of deprivation, but constitutes, in itself, a sufficient condition for triggering collective protest mobilization. This mobilization can arise even in contexts where there is no explicit class consciousness, no assumed revolutionary ideology, and no organized leadership. In other words, the direct and continuous experience of the lack of essential resources – such as sufficient income, housing, food, health or basic education – can generate collective

responses aimed at social transformation, without the need for prior ideological or structural mediation.

P5 – No need for relative deprivation

The collective political mobilization that arises as a result of objective material deprivation does not necessarily require that the individuals or groups affected establish comparisons with other social sectors, nor that they perceive a situation of relative injustice.

In other words, the direct experience of the lack of resources essential for a dignified life – such as sufficient income, housing, food, health or basic education – constitutes, in itself, a sufficient engine for such mobilization to take place. The absence of comparative reference underlines that collective action can emerge only from the verifiable fact of material misery, without the need for those affected to evaluate their situation in relation to that of other groups or to develop an explicit perception of inequality or injustice.

P6 – Non-impeding alienation

Within the framework of the material conditions that affect collective mobilization, the ideological alienation of the worker, understood in the Hegelian-Marxist sense, does not constitute an insurmountable barrier to political action. Even in contexts where individuals experience a significant degree of alienation, this phenomenon does not necessarily impede their ability to mobilize when the objective conditions of material deprivation reach levels that compromise survival or basic dignity.

Thus, direct and persistent experience of essential deprivations – such as lack of sufficient income, housing, adequate food,

health or basic education – can overcome the paralyzing effects of ideological alienation. In this way, although class consciousness, revolutionary ideology or the existence of organized leaderships may be absent, the pressure exerted by objective material deprivation acts as a sufficient trigger for the emergence of collective responses aimed at social transformation.

In other words, although the ideological and cultural superstructure can contribute to normalizing inequality and perpetuating the existing order, it cannot indefinitely neutralize the consequences of material conditions incompatible with social reproduction.

P7 – Superstructure boundary

The ideological-cultural superstructure, understood as the set of values, beliefs and discourses that shape the social perception of reality, plays a fundamental role in the normalization of inequality within society. Through symbolic mechanisms and legitimizing narratives, it is capable of shaping the interpretation that individuals and groups make of their material situation, dampening the perception of deprivation or injustice and delaying the emergence of collective political responses.

However, the superstructure's capacity to perpetuate the acceptance of inequality and contain social tensions is not unlimited. When material conditions reach a critical threshold of incompatibility with social reproduction—that is, when the lack of essential resources compromises survival or basic dignity—the influence of ideological mechanisms is insufficient to neutralize the objective consequences of deprivation. In

these contexts, the direct and persistent experience of material misery imposes itself on legitimizing discourses, eroding the effectiveness of cultural normalization and opening the way to the possibility of social mobilization to political mobilization aimed at social transformation.

Thus, the superstructure can delay the irruption of collective action, but it cannot indefinitely prevent adverse material conditions from acting as an engine of social responses. The limit of the superstructure lies, therefore, in its inability to permanently nullify the effects of objective material deprivation when it threatens the very reproduction of social life.

P8 – Institutional failure

The persistence or aggravation of objective material deprivation within a society should be interpreted as the manifestation of a structural failure in the functioning of the political and economic institutions responsible for guaranteeing social minimums. These institutions, whose main task is to ensure access to essential resources such as income, housing, adequate food, health and basic education, show their inadequacy or ineffectiveness when significant sectors of the population see their survival or basic dignity compromised in a sustained way over time.

This institutional failure is not limited to a specific or circumstantial deficiency, but reveals a systemic inability to respond to fundamental material needs, which, in turn, generates conditions conducive to collective political mobilization.

The inadequacy of institutional mechanisms to correct or reverse objective material deprivation allows it to become chronic, eroding the legitimacy of structures of representation and accountability, and opening the way to social responses aimed at transforming existing conditions.

P9 – Closure of institutional channels

The closure or perception of ineffectiveness of the institutional channels of representation, accountability and democratic correctness constitutes a determining factor in the dynamics of social response to objective material deprivation. When citizens perceive that the formal ways to express demands, correct injustices or hold those who hold political and economic power accountable are insufficient, inoperative or directly absent, there is a profound erosion of trust in the institutional system.

This situation implies that the mechanisms established to channel discontent and articulate collective solutions cease to fulfil their functioning, generating a vacuum of effective political mediation. In this scenario, the probability of forms of direct action – demonstrations, spontaneous protests or even rebellions – increases exponentially, as social actors identify that there are no viable institutional alternatives to meet their material needs or basic demands.

Thus, the closure of institutional channels not only reflects a structural failure in the functioning of institutions, but also acts as a catalyst for autonomous social mobilization, by shifting conflict resolution from the regulated sphere of institutional politics to forms of "direct political action", motivated by the urgency and persistence of objective material deprivation.

P10 – Structural spontaneity of civic rebellions

Civic rebellions that arise in contexts of objective material deprivation have a distinctive characteristic: although their immediate outbreak can be perceived as spontaneous, this spontaneity is determined by the previous accumulation of adverse material conditions. In other words, the collective reaction of citizens does not respond only to isolated events, but is the result of a structural process in which material shortages have intensified and become chronic over time.

The immediacy with which these rebellions are unleashed responds to a point of social saturation, in which the persistence or aggravation of objective material deprivation – in the absence of effective institutional channels for representation and democratic correctness – generates direct political mobilization. This phenomenon shows that the spontaneity of social responses has a structural foundation, linked to the inability of political and economic institutions to guarantee social minimums and to the erosion of trust in the institutional system.

In this way, collective action does not come out of nowhere, but is the logical consequence of a process of accumulation of deprivations and institutional failures, where the logic of the system ceases to offer viable solutions and social actors opt for forms of direct political action such as demonstrations, protests or rebellion.

P11 – Analytic exclusion

The Theory of Objective Material Deprivation (TPMO) establishes an important analytical exclusion, delimiting the scope of its application. In particular, the TPMO is not adequate

to analyse those contexts in which there are organised political movements capable of transforming objective material deprivation into institutionalised class consciousness before a rebellious irruption occurs. That is, the theory does not contemplate the scenarios in which collective action arises as a result of previous processes of political organization, ideological development, and institutional articulation of social demands.

This exclusion implies that the TPMO focuses on cases where material deprivation leads to spontaneous and structurally determined mobilizations, in the absence of organized political mediations that convert deprivation into class consciousness. Therefore, the theory does not address situations in which material deprivation has already been systematically channelled and resignified through political movements that have managed to institutionalize that consciousness before open conflict erupts.

P12 – Central thesis: Consequences of the absence of political mediation

In the Theory of Objective Material Deprivation (TPMO), the central thesis holds that, when there are no effective political mediation mechanisms, the persistent deterioration of objective material conditions generates, with high probability, social explosions that represent the limit form of political action of the excluded sectors.

This approach is based on the idea that objective material deprivation not only produces social unrest, but that, in the absence of institutional channels capable of representing and democratically correcting these shortcomings, a saturation point is produced. It is at this moment that collective responses

cease to be channelled through conventional channels and are transformed into spontaneous mobilizations – such as demonstrations, protests or rebellions – a direct result of the accumulation and chronification of material deprivation.

Thus, the TPMO stresses that collective action is not merely an isolated or punctual reaction, but the inevitable consequence of the persistence of adverse material conditions and the failure of institutions to guarantee social minimums. In this context, the absence of effective political mediation acts as a catalyst that precipitates social unrest, since exclusion and the erosion of trust in the institutional system drive social actors to resort to forms of direct political action.

Taken together, these propositions clarify and resolve the theoretical tension between the classical Marxist perspective, Gurr's interpretation, and the Theory of Objective Material Deprivation (TPMO). Far from being opposed, they show that alienation and ideological mediation are effective until objective material deprivation reaches a critical threshold. From that point on, collective action arises not so much from a previous awareness, but from the impossibility of continuing to endure structural misery, thus shifting the explanatory axis towards the immediate materiality of social experience.

Then there are the societies where there were political parties or movements capable of transforming "accepted perception of inequality" into "social consciousness" for social transformation. There in those societies, leaders and vanguard political movements helped to turn poor people aware of their objective material poverty, into class-conscious poor people capable of understanding that, without their participation in power, without changes in the system, or changes in the system that splendidly and almost exclusively serves the minority, the majority has no possibility of access to real democracy: that which

also attends to the distribution of income, while at the same time dealing with the distribution of work and its responsibilities, and access to education and culture, and to the private property that one's own work gives, and personal freedom, and to safeguard the right to free expression and other human and civil rights.

Direct democracy existed at its birth for Athenian citizens to elect their direct representatives (in the hope that the majority of citizens will elect a ruler for the majority of citizens...), to expect – and if not, to demand – that they govern with transparency, or to dismiss bad rulers and also demand an explanation from them (Ferrada de Noli, 2023; 2025).

Formalization in quasi-axiomatic notation of the Theory of Objective Material Deprivation – TPMO

1. Preliminary definitions

The Theory of Objective Material Deprivation (MPW) is based on a series of definitions that precisely delimit the fundamental concepts used:

D1. Vulnerable population (V):

A vulnerable population is understood as the set of social agents whose daily material reproduction depends critically on essential goods provided, either directly or indirectly, by the State. These goods include, among others, food, transportation, work, health and education.

D2. Objective material deprivation (OMP):

A structural state in which the vulnerable population lacks the minimum material means indispensable for the daily reproduction of life, regardless of subjective expectations or comparisons between social classes.

D3. Essential Regressive Policy (ERP):

It is defined as any state measure that reduces the effective access of the vulnerable population to the goods necessary for material reproduction. Examples of ERPs include increases in transport, food, energy prices or reductions in real wages.

D4. Civic Rebellion (RC):

A form of spontaneous and non-centrally planned collective action, which emerges as a direct response to the application of an essential regressive policy under conditions of objective material deprivation.

2. Fundamental Axioms

The TPMO is based on a set of axioms that structure its theoretical framework:

Axiom 1 – Sufficient material condition:

In any society (S) characterized by high structural inequality, if there is objective material deprivation of the vulnerable population and an essential regressive policy is implemented, then the emergence of a civic rebellion is possible and probable.

$\forall S$ societies with high structural inequality, if $PMO(V,S) \wedge PRE(S) \rightarrow \diamond RC(S)$

In highly unequal societies, the combination of objective material deprivation and essential regressive politics makes civic rebellion possible and likely.

Axiom 2 – Independence of relative perception:

The occurrence of civic rebellion is independent of the subjective perception of relative deprivation with respect to other groups.

$RC(S) \perp PR(S)$ (where PR = subjective relative deprivation).

The occurrence of CR is independent of comparative perception with other groups.

Axiom 3 – Structural spontaneity:

When there is objective material deprivation, civic rebellion emerges without the need for prior party leadership. The spontaneity of these phenomena does not imply the absence of a cause, but the existence of a structural cause.

$PMO(V,S) \rightarrow RC(S)$ emerges without previous party leadership.

Spontaneity is not the absence of a cause, but the presence of a structural cause.

Axiom 4 – Militarization as a normative amplifier:

The deployment of the Army in the control of public order, far from neutralizing the civic rebellion, contributes to moralizing it, giving it moral legitimacy in the eyes of the population.

$Militarization(S) \wedge RC(S) \rightarrow Moral\ Legitimacy(RC)$

The use of the Army in public order does not neutralize, but rather moralizes the rebellion.

3. Corollaries

The following corollaries are derived from the above axioms:

C1 (Predictive):

The quantitative increase in poverty generates a qualitative increase in social conflict.

C2 (Normative):

State violence exercised under conditions of objective material deprivation constitutes a prior violation of the moral contract, and cannot be considered a legitimate response.

C3 (Chilean Historic):

In the Chilean case, an empirical recurrence of civic rebellion is observed when the State intervenes negatively in essential goods.

4. Right-Wing Liberal and Libertarian Objections and Their Philosophical Responses

1. Liberal objections

Liberal objection 1: "Poverty does not explain violence; there are poorer countries without outbreaks."

Faced with the assertion that poverty alone is not enough to explain violent episodes, the answer is that the theory presented is not based on poverty as an isolated phenomenon. Rather, the explanation combines objective material deprivation (PMO), regressive austerity policy (PRE), high inequality, and institutional denial. It is not poverty "in the abstract", but the active interruption of previously existing minimum conditions, which triggers conflict.

Liberal Objection 2: "Violence is always illegitimate; the State must impose order."

From a critical perspective inspired by Rawls, it is recalled that civil disobedience can be justified when institutions fail and the less advantaged bear the consequences. He goes further by stating that, when the social order prevents the material reproduction of life, rebellion is not pathological, but defensive. Thus, the legitimacy of violence is assessed in terms of the capacity of order to guarantee basic material conditions.

2. Right-Wing Libertarian Objections

Right-Libertarian Objection 1: "The state is not responsible for poverty; the market is neutral."

The response emphasizes that sectors that are fundamental to life, such as transportation, minimum wage, energy, or health, do not function as free markets, but are structures regulated by political decisions. Therefore, any policy of regressive austerity is a political decision and not a natural phenomenon, which invalidates the supposed neutrality of the market when it comes to essential goods.

Right-Libertarian Objection 2: "Protests are manipulated by the left."

Empirical evidence shows that in historical contexts such as 1905, 1907, 1949, 1957, and 2019, political parties have reacted to protests, but have not led them. In this way, the historical repetition of these episodes refutes the conspiratorial hypothesis of partisan manipulation.

3. Technocratic objection

"These are problems of communication, not of justice."

Following Sen's approach, it is argued that justice is not only a procedure, but the effective ability to live with dignity. If people are unable to travel, feed or work, the policy has failed, regardless of the quality of institutional communication (Sen, 1999; 2009).

Conclusion

This work has proposed the Theory of Objective Material Deprivation (TPMO) as a normative framework for the analysis of political injustice and the structural conditions associated with civic mobilisation.

In contrast to approaches focused on relative deprivation and the primacy of the subjective perception of grievance, it has been argued that there are *objective material thresholds* whose transgression constitutes a primary form of political injustice, regardless of the formal correctness of procedures or institutional discourse.

In dialogue with Amartya Sen's capabilities approach, it has been argued that the evaluation of justice cannot be exhausted in procedural criteria or in the mere existence of formal rights, but must attend to the *effective possibility of converting these rights into basic functionings*. The TPMO specifies this approach by identifying situations in which such capacities are materially impossible and by arguing that such blockages not only have normative relevance, but also directly affect the conditions of legitimacy of the political order.

From this point of view, the theory allows an analytical distinction between objective material deprivation, subjective perception of injustice and collective action, without reducing one action to the other. Its scope is not predictive in the strict sense, but interpretative

and normative: it offers a criterion for evaluating political orders based on their material conditions of possibility and for understanding the emergence of civic conflicts as an expression of structural failures in the material organization of social life. In this sense, the TPMO aspires to contribute to the clarification of the links between justice, political legitimacy and material conditions of existence in the field of normative political philosophy.

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